

Role of Personal Factors on Principals' Administrative Effectiveness in Secondary Schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council

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Abstract

This study examined influence of personal factors on principals' administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council. The research design adopted was descriptive survey. Three research questions and one hypothesis guided the study. Questionnaire titled, "Influence of Personal and School Factors on Principals' Administrative Effectiveness in Secondary Schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council (IPFPAE) Questionnaire, was the instrument used. The sample size was 320 teachers. Data analysis was by mean score, standard deviation and Pearson-Product-Moment Correlation. Findings of the study indicated that to a very high extent gender influence on administrative effectiveness is low, experience on the job and principals' higher qualification and verse knowledge do make them to be more effective. Based on the findings, the study recommended that leadership position should be given to only persons that merits it as against resorting to gender stereotype, which favours male teachers more, deployment of principals should be on the basis of experience and there should be leadership development for the principals to enable them broaden their horizons in relevant administrative areas.

Key words: *Personal factors, school factors, principals administrative effectiveness*

Introduction

There is trading of blames on the cause of declining standard of education at the secondary level. The point is that while some people blame the government for its inability to make provisions for adequate teaching and learning outcomes in schools, others push the blame on factors bordering on lapses in leadership at the school level. Odufowokan (2011) affirmed that education is capital intensive and once the necessary resources are not pumped into the system, be human or material, it could lead to declining standards of education. This is the reason why resources should not be spared so that quality leadership (principals) could be enthroned in the system. The essence of provision of quality resources is to ensure that no imbalance exists and lapses of

over-crowded classrooms, poor and shoddy inspections and supervision from principals, obsolete teaching techniques, and lack of systematic planning, particularly at state and local government levels are avoided (Odufowokan, 2011). The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2004) was categorical about the importance of secondary education in the task of nation building, hence, ideas from various areas of national development are crucial in planning the provision of education for the nation. To this end, Udeozor (2004) asserted that no education programme can succeed without highly motivated and committed members of staff. This has implications for principals' effectiveness for the successful implementation of educational objectives, which is dependent on the principals' leadership abilities. This is why an effective leader is seen as someone who influences his or her group to success (Udeozor, 2004).

Udeozor (2004) also stated that the performance of a group is contingent upon the leader influencing the group members to develop positive attitudes towards job performance, which is extremely important for the smooth functioning of schools. This is where the question of motivation comes into play, and studies have proven that for a system to succeed, the staff must be adequately motivated. Motivation though a driving force that energizes and influences behaviour of people, can only be achieved based on personal and school factors (Ajayi, 2001). This brings about the question of what constitute principal effectiveness. The answer to the question of what Constitutes principals' effectiveness lies in the personal, as well as school factors. For instance, principals' age, gender, experience and qualifications are various attributes termed as personal factors and these could define the effectiveness of the school principal (Michael, 2011). Achibong (2015) also corroborated Michael by stating that certain personal variables such as age, years of experience, and personal dispositions could bring about leadership effectiveness. Another important factor that could enhance or hinder principals' effectiveness is school size. This defines the largeness or otherwise of the school (Adeyemi, 2012). In addition, Achibong (2015) upheld the view that leadership and principal-ship are synonymous, and in education, personnel management implies managing followers. The principals' management practices generate a positive or negative attitude towards work. This means principal's leadership effectiveness is important in managing activities in secondary schools.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on expectancy and goal setting theories. The expectancy theory was developed by Victor Vroom in 1964. In this theory, it was affirmed that three main issues are necessary for goal attainment, which are efforts, outcome, and valence. According to Vroom, (1964) Effort borders on the ability to perform, interest, and intelligence. Outcome depends on potential reward such as payment, chances for promotion, and other welfare packages. Valence is an instrument that promotes efforts. This motivational theory argues that principals will tend to be very hardworking because of the expectation of getting promotion to improve on their living standard. The school should equally encourage them so that the (school) inputs will not be discouraging and then turn out to be negative on the principals' performance.

The goal setting theory of motivation was developed by Edwin Locke in 1960s, and it embarked upon two main areas. These are directing attention and prompting action. Within the concept of these two, goal setting theory attempts to mobilize efforts, increase persistence and then

encourage development strategies in order to achieve results. The success of this theory in any organization depends on developing and setting of realizable goals within a specific time frame. Prompting action on the other hand involves activities to be carried out towards ensuring the realization of the goals set out from the very beginning. The main objective focus should be positive students' academic performance as topmost. This should be followed by various steps and strategies that could ensure that the main goal is attained. This is where administrative effectiveness of the principals come into focus.

The implication of this study is that the system need to put modalities in place to motivate those principal factors into converting such into creating efforts that could guarantee administrative effectiveness. more also, the objective of goal setting is to ensure that management, staff, and students are all motivated positively in order to perform what is expected of them so that the desired results could be achieved. This implies that principals need to develop strategies that could bring about the attainment of both schools' and national education objectives within their jurisdiction. The deployment of the strategies is what leads to administrative effectiveness.

Concept of Principals Personal Factors

Every leader has certain attributes that define his or her personality. These attributes have a way of influencing reasoning, actions, relationship with others, leadership style and role performance in organization. These are gender, experience and qualification.

- **Gender Factor**

The Beijing conference in China had affirmed the crucial nature of women empowerment, and to this end, Obasi (2006) explained that female subjugation in a male dominated society often leads to economic downturn and also affirmed that more than 65% of males are economically active compared to only less than 35% females. This creates an imbalance in the system. To checkmate the imbalance, Oke (2005) explained that education is the only tool that can help in determining the distribution of employment and income for both present and future generations. The study of Paustian-Underdahl, Walker and Woehr (2014) showed that when all leadership contexts are considered, men and women do not differ in perceived leadership effectiveness. Ibukun, Oyewole and Abe (2011) also indicated that no significant difference existed between leadership effectiveness of male and female principals in the performance of their duties. This means, when they are given all necessary support and resources, their performance may not differ much.

- **Principals Experience**

The role performance of the principals become easier and interesting as the principals grow on the job. Queensland State Department of Education, Training and Employment (QSDETE) (2012) stated that teaching is a career that provides challenges, excitement, personal reward and a chance to encourage and support others to achieve their goals. The department affirmed that though the major academic quality of a teacher lies in his or her certification but many other personal qualities occur based on experience. As a matter of fact, principal experience remains the livewire that determines principal's ability to deliver on the job (King-Rice, 2003). For instance, the study of Green, Chavez, Lopez and Gonzalez (2011) found that experience contribute to outstanding leadership integrity, team-oriented, participative, humane-oriented and diplomacy in the school. The study of Dodson (2006) also affirmed that as principals gained experience during their

leadership training and during their principal preparation programs, such experience enhances their effectiveness.

- **Principals Qualification**

The concept of principals' qualification is broad based. Valerie (2011) believed that principals' qualification often stemmed from the attributes that make teachers to be great teachers. Ramsden (2003) simply averred that the aim of teaching is simply to make student learning possible. To teach is to make an assumption about what and how the student learns; therefore, to teach well implies learning about students' learning behaviours. The assumption is that someone that has an M.Ed qualification will be better than someone with B.Sc. (Ed) or BA (Ed) honours degree qualifications in terms of possessing leadership quality. This equally applies that someone that has a doctorate degree will be better than someone with a Masters or first degree (Goodman, 2008). The study of Akinola and Adebakin (2016) confirmed that the quality of the school principal in terms of qualification had positive influence on school effectiveness. Also, the study of Sawati, Anwar and Majoka (2013) found positive relationship between principals' qualifications and their effectiveness.

Concept of Principals Administrative Effectiveness

Administrative effectiveness is viewed as a process of deploying strategies to achieve the set goals of a school and relating them to the general goals of education in Nigeria (FRN, 2004). Administration is a social process designed to ensure cooperation, participation and involvement of others in order to achieve set goals in the school (Obasi & Asodike, 2007). Every organization and department is structured in groups of subordinates acting under the control and guidance of a leader. This brings about effectiveness in the running of such organisation. In a school setting for instance, the principal tend to function effectively in the discharge of administrative duties through various strategies such as role performance; school community relation; physical and financial management; instructional programme; staff personnel administration; students' personnel administration; and maintaining discipline in school (Peretomode, 2005).

Statement of Problem

Educational administrators face a lot of challenges in the management of secondary schools. They are confronted with the scope of their authority, decision-making and obtaining feed-back by establishing a conducive atmosphere and stimulating environment that can enhance the realization of set goals. The emphasis is that achieving certain goals and objectives entails possessing the ability and the know-how (Aina & Olanipekun, 2015). Against this background, this study seeks to examine whether there is influence or not of personal and school factors on principals' administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council.

Purpose of this Study

The main purpose of this study is to examine influence of personal factors on principals' administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

- i. find out the extent to which gender factor influence principals' administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council;

- ii. establish the extent to which experience influence principals' administrative effectiveness in Abuja Municipal Area Council;
- iii. find out if academic qualification has any influence on principals' administrative effectiveness in Abuja Municipal Area Council

Research Questions

The following research questions served as guide to this study:

1. What is the extent to which gender factor influence principals' administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council?
2. What is the extent to which experience influence principals' administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council?
3. What is the influence of academic qualification on principals' administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council?

Hypothesis

The following research hypothesis served as guide to this study:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between personal factors and principals' administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council.

Methodology

The research approach adopted in this study was descriptive survey. According to FCT Education Resource Centre, the population of senior Secondary Schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council is 24, with population of 1639 teachers. 320 teachers were purposively chosen as sample size. Black (2010) affirmed that purposive sampling technique also called judgmental sampling is a form of sampling in which respondents are selected based on the researcher's judgment. This was considered appropriate in line with Research Advisor (2006) method of determining sample size, and 20 teachers participated in each of the 16 schools selected. The researcher developed a questionnaire called, "Influence of Personal Factors on Principals' Administrative Effectiveness in Secondary Schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council (IPFPAE) Questionnaire. IPFPAE consisted of two sections A and B. Section A solicited information on the personal data of teachers while section B contains a four point Likert scale fourteen (14) item questionnaire developed by the researcher. The questionnaire items were arranged in two sub-headings to seek information on the variables being studied. The instrument was given to two specialists in Educational Management for validation. Their corrections formed the basis of the final instrument used for the main study. To ensure content validity, a pilot test was carried out by administering the instrument to 30 teachers in three schools (10 from each school) outside the study area. The test was calculated using Cronbach alpha to establish the reliability of the questionnaire, and the reliability coefficient of 0.88 was obtained. The mean rating of each questionnaire item was determined by scoring each response as follows: Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2, and strongly Disagree (SD) = 1. Also, Very High Extent (VHE) = 4, High Extent (HE) = 3, Low Extent (LE) = 2, and Very Low Extent (VLE) = 1. Mean score of 2.5 and above implies an acceptance or agreement while any mean value less than 2.5 signifies disagreement. Pearson Product Moment-Correlation was used to test the hypothesis. P-value in relation to 0.05 level of significance was used to interpret the hypotheses. Where a p-value was less than 0.05, the null

hypothesis was rejected, but where a p-value was greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis was accepted.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the extent to which gender factor influence principals' administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council?

Table 1 shows the items on the extent of influence of gender on principals' administrative effectiveness from the research questionnaire.

Table 1: Extent of Influence of Gender on Principals' Administrative Effectiveness

Items on Gender	Male=163		Female=157		Decision
	Sd	\bar{x}	Sd	\bar{x}	
1. School leaders always emerge more among the men folks	0.80	2.40	0.81	2.39	Disagree
2. Male principals tend to influence subordinates more easily.	0.81	2.26	0.84	2.43	Disagree
3. Male characteristics (aggression, self-reliance, dominance, and rationality) prove positivity in leadership effectiveness.	0.84	2.55	0.76	2.54	Agree
4. Some good leaders do emerge among the women folks who are diligent and development minded.	0.80	2.59	0.75	2.55	Agree
5. Women who are well empowered are better leaders than men.	0.81	2.44	0.83	2.40	Disagree
6. Low rating of women in human capital development affects female principal leadership effectiveness.	0.82	2.55	0.79	2.55	Agree
	0.81	2.46	0.80	2.48	Disagree

Table 1 showing mean scores of 2.40, 2.26, 2.55, 2.59, 2.44 and 2.55 in support of male principals and 2.39, 2.43, 2.54, 2.55, 2.40 and 2.55 in support of female principals for items 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, and 15 respectively. The overall mean scores of 2.46 and 2.48 and a standard deviation of 0.81 and 0.80 respectively around their means show that the respondents are of the opinion that influence of principals' gender on administrative effectiveness is low. This means that principals' gender does not specifically influence leadership effectiveness.

Research Question 2: What is the extent to which experience influence principals' administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council?

Table 2 shows the items on the extent of influence of experience on principals' administrative effectiveness from the research questionnaire.

Table 2: Extent of Influence of Experience on Principals' Administrative Effectiveness

		VHE	HE	LE	VLE	Sd	\bar{x}	Decision
7.	Being the livewire that determines principal's ability to deliver on the job.	125	140	35	20	0.68	3.16	Agree
8.	Enhancing principals' interpersonal relationship and ability to manage people and time.	132	125	38	25	0.76	3.14	Agree
9.	Influencing of subordinates or group of individuals to achieve set goals and objectives.	146	119	25	30	0.69	3.19	Agree
10.	Aiding the determination of the leadership styles to deploy in any given situation.	136	122	27	35	0.75	3.12	Agree
						0.72	3.15	Accept

Table 2 showing mean scores of 3.16, 3.14, 3.19, and 3.12 for items 16, 17, 18 and 19 respectively, as well as overall mean scores of 3.15 and a standard deviation of 0.72 around the mean shows that the respondents have accepted that to a very high extent, experience on the job influence principals' administrative effectiveness. This means that the administrative effectiveness in senior secondary schools with experienced principals is very high compared to schools with inexperienced principals.

Research Question 3: What is the influence of academic qualification on principals' administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council?

Table 2 shows the items on influence of academic qualification on principals' administrative effectiveness as derived from the research questionnaire.

Table 3: Influence of Academic Qualification on Principals' Effectiveness

		SA	A	D	SD	Sd	\bar{x}	Decision
11.	Higher qualification has the potential to expose the principal to be more effective in carrying out his or her duties in the school.	133	126	38	23	0.73	3.15	Agree
12.	Principals that are verse in their knowledge area are associated with greater goal attainment.	128	124	32	36	0.71	3.06	Agree
13.	Principals with higher qualifications in education are more motivated on the job which enhance administrative effectiveness.	125	132	27	36	0.83	3.08	Agree

14. Principals with higher qualifications in education are focused and have no divided attention regarding prospect of another job.	137	120	33	30	0.74	3.14	Agree
					0.75	3.11	Accept

Table 6 showing mean scores of 3.15, 3.06, 3.08, and 3.14 for items 20, 21, 22 and 23 respectively, as well as overall mean scores of 3.11 and a standard deviation of 0.75 around the mean shows that the respondents have accepted that higher qualification has the potential to expose principal to be more effective in carrying out their duties in the school, principals that are verse in their knowledge area are associated with greater attainment of school aims and objectives, principals with higher qualifications in education are more motivated on the job, which enhances administrative effectiveness, and principals with higher qualifications in education are focused and have no divided attention regarding prospect of another job.

Test of Hypothesis

Ho: There is no significant relationship between personal factors and principals' administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in AMAC.

Table 4: Relationship of Personal Factors and Principals' Administrative Effectiveness

Variable	\bar{X}	Sd	r	p-value	Df	Decision
Experience	2.91	0.76				
Admin.	3.20	0.74	.369	.000	39	Significant
Effectiveness						

**(P < 0.05 level of significance)*

Table 5 shows the results of the test of significant relationship between personal factors and principals' administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council. The coefficient obtained was 0.369, with a p-value = 0, which is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that a significant relationship exists between personal factors and principals' administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council.

Discussion

Analysis of finding (Table 1) indicated that principals' gender does not specifically influence leadership effectiveness in senior secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council. This finding agrees with the study of Paustian-Underdahl, Walker, and Woehr (2014) who showed that when all leadership contexts are considered, men and women do not differ in perceived leadership effectiveness. This is also in line with Ibukun, Oyewole, and Abe (2011) who also indicated that no significant difference existed between leadership effectiveness of male and female principals in the performance of their duties. This is because when the necessary provisions are made for the school principals, irrespective of gender, they will be effective in the discharge of their leadership duties.

Analysis of finding (Table 2) indicated that experience on the job influence principals' administrative effectiveness in senior secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council. This finding agrees with the finding of Green, Chavez, Lopez and Gonzalez (2011) found that experience contribute to outstanding leadership integrity, team-oriented, participative, humane-oriented and diplomacy in the school. Dodson (2006) also affirmed that as principals gained experience during their leadership training and during their principal preparation programs, such experience enhances their effectiveness.

Analysis of research question three (Table 3) indicated that higher qualification influence principals' administrative effectiveness in senior secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council. This finding agrees with that of Akinola and Adebakin (2016) who confirmed that the quality of the school principal in terms of qualification had positive influence on school effectiveness, as well as Sawati, Anwar and Majoka (2013) found positive relationship between principals' qualifications and their effectiveness.

Also, the test of hypothesis indicated that a significant relationship exists between personal factors and principals' administrative effectiveness in senior secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council.

Conclusion

Based on the finding of this research, it was concluded that a significant relationship exists between personal factors and principals' administrative effectiveness in senior secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council. The implication is that influence of principals' gender on administrative effectiveness is low and can be negligible because gender does not specifically influence leadership effectiveness. More so, to a very high extent, experience and principals' higher qualification and verse knowledge could make them to be more effective in carrying out their duties.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the recommendations proposed are that:

1. Leadership position should be given to whoever that merits it as against being gender stereotype in favour of male teachers. This will further empower female into striving to be the best if there is no discrimination against them.
2. Deployment of principals should be on the basis of experience and not deployment of inexperience people based on nepotism or corrupt practices. This means the system should be organized in such a way that only the best people who have proven their worth should be given leadership position to head schools.
3. Government and school management should endeavour to have a programme for skill updating and leadership development for the principals so that as they possess higher qualifications, their horizon will be broadened, they will have high sense of creativity and by so doing be better equipped in the contemporary ways of administering schools for higher administrative effectiveness.

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